

225-1 Activity of pyrolysis-derived bio-oil phase from the pericarp of *Syagrus coronata* (Licuri), *Terminalia catappa* (Almond) and *Cocos nucifera* (Coconut) against the emerging fungus *Candida auris*

Autores:

Karen Nardy (UFF - Universidade Federal Fluminense) ; Deborah Santos Cintra (UFF - Universidade Federal Fluminense) ; Michele Valente (UFF - Universidade Federal Fluminense) ; Gilberto Alves Romeiro (UFF - Universidade Federal Fluminense) ; Pâmela Oliveira (UFF - Universidade Federal Fluminense) ; Bruno Salarini (UFF - Universidade Federal Fluminense) ; Leonardo Honorato (UFRJ - Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro) ; Joshua Nosanchuk (EINSTEIN - Albert Einstein College of Medicine) ; Daniel Zamith-miranda (EINSTEIN - Albert Einstein College of Medicine) ; Marcia Ribeiro (UFF - Universidade Federal Fluminense) ; Allan Guimarães (UFF - Universidade Federal Fluminense, UFRJ - Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro)

Resumo:

Candida auris is an emerging fungus that has been highlighted as a global threat recently, due to notification of several cases of nosocomial and invasive candidemia reported worldwide, in addition to a high mortality rate. Recently, *Candida auris* has been widely reported for its multi-resistance capacity to several classes of antifungals on the market, such as fluconazole and other azoles, amphotericin B and echinocandins, making its clinical management even more problematic. Given this scenario, there is currently an urgent need for research and development of new and more efficient alternatives for the environmental control, elimination and therapeutic strategies for *Candida auris*. This study aimed to evaluate the anti-*Candida auris* activity of the pyrolysis-derived bio-oil aqueous phase from the pericarp of *Syagrus coronata* (Licuri), *Terminalia catappa* (Almond) and *Cocos nucifera* (Coconut). Furthermore, susceptibility testing of the extract fractions using clinical strains of *Candida auris* was performed through evaluation by antifungigram (susceptibility testing) and disk volatilization. Among the tested bio-oils aqueous phase, besides anti-candida performance of all, the Licuri had the lowest minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) value as well as the one with the largest inhibition halo diameter and lowest colony forming unit (CFU) count in comparison to control ($p < 0.001$). The resistant strain MMC1 showed MIC of 0,141mg/ml, whereas the susceptible strain MMC2 showed MIC of 0,0351mg/ml. Also, among the other ten clinical strains of *Candida auris* tested, was observed MIC range of 0,281-0,0351. The highest percentage of halo growth inhibition zone, according to the dilution factor, was observed at MMC1 strains (concentration cell/ml), with an average of MMC1 (BOAP I, II, III: 99,08%; 99,19%; 98,9%) and MMC2 (BOAP I,II,III:99,44%; 99,94%; 99,89%) The Licuri extract fractionations demonstrated that the best activity was retained in the aqueous phase and could be partially extracted with chloroform. The complex composition of the active fractions was also evaluated by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). It was concluded that Licuri displayed the best antifungal activity against the emerging fungus *Candida auris*, constituting a promising new alternative for environmental decontamination and a potential natural therapeutic option against *Candida auris*.

Palavras-chave:

Candida auris, antifungals, natural extracts, bio-oil, pyrolysis

Agência de fomento:

CAPES, CNPQ, FAPERJ